
THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING FLS

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Abstract: Language learning is a complex process that requires learners to acquire not only knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, but also the ability to use language in real-life situations. In order to achieve this goal, language teachers need to create a learning environment that is engaging, interactive, and communicative. Understanding the importance of these kinds of activities, this article is devoted to analyze the role of communicative activities with details.

Key words: communicative activities, role plays, communicative teaching.

Introduction

One way to achieve this is through the use of interactive activities in teaching foreign languages (FLs). Interactive activities refer to any task or exercise that requires learners to actively participate in the learning process by using the language in meaningful ways. These activities can take many forms, such as role-plays, group discussions, games, simulations, and project-based learning. The purpose of this paper is to explore the role of interactive activities in teaching FLs and to discuss their benefits and challenges. We will examine the theoretical foundations of interactive activities, review empirical studies on their effectiveness, and provide practical suggestions for implementing them in FL classrooms. The paper will conclude with a discussion of the implications of interactive activities for FL teaching and learning.

The role of communicative activities in teaching foreign languages

The role of communicative activities in teaching foreign languages is crucial for language learners to develop their language skills in real-life situations. Communicative activities refer to any task or exercise that requires learners to use the language in meaningful ways, such as role-plays, group discussions, games, simulations, and project-based learning. These activities help learners to practice their language skills in a context that mirrors real-life situations, allowing them to develop their communicative competence.

The theoretical foundations of communicative activities can be traced back to the communicative approach to language teaching, which emphasizes the importance of communication as the ultimate goal of language learning. According to this approach, language learning should focus on developing learners' ability to use the language effectively in a variety of social contexts. Communicative activities are designed to

provide learners with opportunities to practice using the language in a communicative way, allowing them to develop their communicative competence.

Empirical studies have shown that communicative activities are effective in promoting language learning. For example, a study by Richards and Rodgers (2001) found that communicative activities were more effective than traditional grammar-focused activities in promoting language learning. Another study by Nunan (1991) found that communicative activities were effective in promoting learners' motivation and engagement in language learning.

Implementing communicative activities in foreign language classrooms can be challenging, as it requires teachers to create a learning environment that is engaging, interactive, and communicative. Teachers need to design activities that are relevant to learners' interests and needs, and that provide opportunities for learners to use the language in meaningful ways. Teachers also need to provide feedback and support to learners, helping them to develop their language skills and overcome any difficulties they may encounter.

There are several practical suggestions for implementing communicative activities in foreign language classrooms. First, teachers should design activities that are relevant to learners' interests and needs, and that provide opportunities for learners to use the language in meaningful ways. Second, teachers should provide feedback and support to learners, helping them to develop their language skills and overcome any difficulties they may encounter. Third, teachers should create a positive learning environment that encourages learners to take risks and make mistakes, as this is an essential part of the language learning process.

In conclusion, the role of communicative activities in teaching foreign languages is crucial for language learners to develop their language skills in real-life situations. Communicative activities provide learners with opportunities to practice using the language in a communicative way, allowing them to develop their communicative competence. Implementing communicative activities in foreign language classrooms can be challenging, but with careful planning and support, teachers can create a learning environment that is engaging, interactive, and communicative.

Some examples for communicative activities

1. Role-plays: In this activity, learners are assigned roles and are required to interact with each other in a simulated real-life situation. For example, a role-play could involve learners acting out a conversation between a customer and a salesperson in a store. This activity helps learners practice their speaking and listening skills in a context that mirrors real-life situations.

2. Group discussions: In this activity, learners are divided into groups and are required to discuss a topic or issue. For example, learners could be asked to discuss the

advantages and disadvantages of social media. This activity helps learners practice their speaking and listening skills, as well as their ability to express opinions and ideas.

3. Games: In this activity, learners play games that require them to use the language in a communicative way. For example, learners could play a game of charades, where they have to act out words or phrases for their teammates to guess. This activity helps learners practice their speaking and listening skills, as well as their ability to think creatively and communicate effectively.

4. Simulations: In this activity, learners are placed in a simulated real-life situation and are required to interact with each other in a way that mirrors that situation. For example, learners could be asked to simulate a job interview. This activity helps learners practice their speaking and listening skills, as well as their ability to handle real-life situations.

5. Project-based learning: In this activity, learners work on a project that requires them to use the language in a communicative way. For example, learners could be asked to create a video or presentation about a topic of their choice. This activity helps learners practice their speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills, as well as their ability to work collaboratively and think critically.

Conclusion

Communicative activities are essential in teaching foreign languages as they provide learners with opportunities to practice using the language in a meaningful and authentic way. These activities help learners develop their communication skills, including speaking, listening, reading, and writing, as well as their ability to express opinions and ideas, work collaboratively, think critically, and handle real-life situations. By engaging in communicative activities, learners become more confident and proficient in using the language, which ultimately leads to better communication and understanding between people from different cultures and backgrounds. Therefore, communicative activities should be an integral part of any foreign language curriculum.

References:

1. Khoshimova, N. A. (2021). ASSOCIATIVE FIELDS OF THE COLLECTIVE AND INDIVIDUAL CONSCIOUS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 436-439.
2. Hashimova, N., & Sattorov, T. (2021). USAGE OF ENGLISH MILITARY TERMINOLOGIES AS A NEUTRAL AND COLLOQUIAL VOCABULARY. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758)*, 2(11), 162-167.
3. Hoshimova, N. A. (2020). Ingliz va o'zbek tillarining funktsional uslublari. *Молодой ученый*, (19), 584-585.

4. Xoshimova, N. (2019). External factors of associations’ individuality. *Scientific journal of the Fergana State University*, 2(2), 134-136.
5. Toirova, N. I. (2019). The significance of the symbols of Mirror and Portrait in teaching Symbolism. *sign*, 1, 22.
6. Mamajanova, M. (2021). MODEL CONCEPT MODELING IN LINGUISTICS TYPES OF LINGUISTIC MODELS. *Экономика и социум*, (1-1), 160-163.
7. Holbekova, M., Mamajonova, M., & Holbekov, S. (2021). COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1), 83-85.
8. Mirzayevna, M. (2021). Innovative technologies in foreign language teaching methodology. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(12), 465-467.
9. Kasimova, G. (2022). IMPORTANCE OF ICE BREAKING ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 117-120.
10. Makhmudovna, K. G. (2022). Creative Strategies to Improve Vocabulary Teaching. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 259-261.
11. Kurbanovna E. N. Application of multimedia and interactive materials in foreign language teaching in non-philological higher educational institutions //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 2 (147). – С. 65-67.
12. Akhmedova, M. (2012). Characteristics of bronchial asthma associated with allergic rhinosinusitis in children. *Medical and Health Science Journal*, 11, 39-43.
13. Ibragimjonovna, A. M. (2022). Developing professional communicative competence of medical students in a foreign language. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 15, 45-50.
14. Isaqjon, T. (2022). Strategies and techniques for improving EFL learners’ reading skills. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(11), 94-99.
15. Mohira, A., & Isakjon, T. (2022). METHODOLOGY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 3, 68-71.
16. Ahundjanova, M. A. (2020). METHODS AND METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE. *Экономика и социум*, (11), 46-49.
17. Ahundjanova, M. (2022). THE NEEDS FOR IMPROVING LEARNERS’AUTONOMY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES—AS A KEY FACTOR TO BOOST LANGUAGE LEARNERS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 390-392.

18. Gafurova, N. I. (2021). Structural-semantic classification of construction terms in English and Uzbek languages. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 571-575.
19. Gafurova, N. (2020). Ҳозирги замон тилшунослигида “Термин” ва унга турлича ёндашувлар. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 1(1), 58-62.
20. Mirzaaliyev, I., & Oxunov, A. (2021). EKVIVALENTSIZ LEKSIKANING O’ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA IFODALANISHI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(6), 209-212.
21. Oxunov, A. O. O. (2021). INGLIZ VA O’ZBEK TILLARIDA UNDOV SO’ZLAR (INTERJECTION) NING IFODALANISHI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 401-406.
22. Abdukhalimova Sarvinozkhon. (2023). HOZIRGI INGLIZ VA O’ZBEK TILLARIDAGI ZIDLOV BOG’LANGAN QO’SHMA GAPLARNING SEMANTIK TAHLILI. *PEDAGOGS Jurnal*, 27(1), 153–157.
23. Абдухалимова, С. (2022). THE CONCEPT AND CONTENT OF INTERCULTURAL DISCOURSE. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(4).
24. Abdumutaljonovna, P. S. (2023). TILSHUNOSLIKDA REKLAMA DISKURSI VA UNING IFODASI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 15(1), 98-101.
25. Pakirdinova, S. (2023). ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDA REKLAMA MATNI VA UNING O’ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(19).
26. Kochkorova, Z. A. Q. (2021). Translation aspects of the verbalizers of the concept of "wedding". *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 989-994.
27. Mirzayev, A., & Oripova, S. (2022). COMMUNICATIVE METHOD—A NEW APPROACH IN THE PRACTICE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 778-783.
28. Ashurali, M. (2022). HOZIRGI KUNDAGI TA’LIM TIZIMIDA ONLAYN TEXNOLOGIYALARGA ASOSLANGAN METODNI TA’LIMGA JORIY QILISHNING AKTUALLIGI. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(13), 25-28.
29. Узакова, Г. З. (2022). КОНЦЕПТ ВА УНИНГ ЛИСОНИЙ ВОҚЕЛАНИШ ЖАРАЁНИ. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(13), 42-45.